

PROSPECTS FOR MODELING THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF STRATEGIES FOR INCREASING THE COMPETITIVENESS OF GRADUATES IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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Annotation: The article explores issues such as the use of competitiveness and management models in the development of strategies to increase the competitiveness of graduates in higher education institutions, and the increased effectiveness of strategic planning of graduate competitiveness.

Keywords: Higher education institutions, graduates, graduate competitiveness, graduate employment, strategic planning, graduate competitiveness of higher education institution.

The main goal of structural changes in recent years regarding the reform of the higher education system in our country is to ensure the comprehensive independence of functioning higher education institutions based on the needs of society in a free market environment, while reducing the state's participation in the activities of the higher education system. At a new stage of reforms on the modernization of the higher education system, which began in 2021, it was established as a priority to bring existing higher education institutions to a new level on the basis of the concept "University 3,0", which is today considered the main concept in the development of universities in the world.

If, as the main aspects that determine the activities of higher educational institutions in the conditions of free competition, first of all, their income and the provision of customer needs for the trained specialists are taken into account, the degree to which the trained specialists can compete with other higher education specialists in the labor market is one of the main factors in the.

Research shows that in modern concepts of modernization of Higher Education, the main focus is on the training of competitive specialists in the labor market, the result of an objective assessment of the effectiveness of university activities is the level of employment of graduates and their career in this area[1].

The processes of professional training of specialists, on the one hand, are regulated on the basis of the requirements of the established state educational standard of Higher Education, territorial and university requirements for the content of training, on the other hand, higher educational institutions should take into account the requirements of employers for the quality of graduates, that is, consumers of specialists Both of the requirements outlined together lead to the understanding that the main goal of the activities of the educational process of higher educational institutions is the formation and development of the competitiveness of graduates corresponding to the requirements of the current and promising labor market[2,3].

Taking into account the above aspects, it was determined that the improvement of the process of training specialists of higher education institutions operating in the research process should be carried out through measures in three main directions (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Formation and development model of graduate competitiveness in the system of higher education system and labor market interaction¹

In the system of interaction of the higher education system and the labor market, measures in the first direction ensuring the formation and development of the competitiveness of graduates should be directed to improving the technology of professional training of graduates, and these measures should be aimed at monitoring and improving the quality of professional training, moving to a two-stage (universal and specialist) educational model, it is advisable to cover activities such as the organization of the process of additional professional education and the improvement of the organization of practical training of students and graduates to Real production conditions[4,5].

¹ Developed by the author.

Measures in the second direction, ensuring the formation and development of the competitiveness of graduates, are measures in the marketing activities of a higher educational institution (marketing Research, PR activities of a higher educational institution, the reaction to changes in demand in the labor market and the educational services market, the study of the demand and supply of specialties in the labor market, – production consists of partnerships and social partnerships and improving university rankings as an indicator of the University's assessment in the labor market) will expand the possibility of qualitatively improving the competitiveness of graduates in the context of their interaction between universities and the labor market[6].

Measures in the third direction, ensuring the formation and development of graduates' competitiveness, should cover activities aimed at improving the socio-psychological and professional adaptation of graduates, such as assistance in adaptation and employment, qualification internships and the organization of internships, deepening mutual cooperation with employers, employment structures, public administration bodies, public organizations and others, retraining and additional educational services[8].

It is advisable for a number of graduates, which allows them to evaluate the results of these activities by higher educational institutions, to develop indicators of competitiveness and evaluate the results and changes achieved in the activities according to these indicators. It is recommended by higher education institutions to develop indicators of the competitiveness of graduates in the form of generalized indicators in the following 3 groups:

1. Indicators of professional qualification of a graduate – diplomas or certificates, rating of a higher educational institution, form of education, success of Education, specialization in a diploma, practical experience, skills, intersecting profiles of professions.
2. Motivational potential of a graduate-motives of Labor behavior, career plans, assessment of the level of Labor potential and established requirements for the place of work, flexibility to personal and collective values, abilities and personal qualities.
3. The marketing potential of a graduate is the level of readiness for status and career levels, adequate behavioral skills and attitudes in the process of employment, and the level of readiness for further professional development and retraining.

In relation to the quality characteristics of graduate specialists prepared by higher education institutions according to the indicated assessment indicators, employers who are participants in the labor market as consumers, in general, make the following 4 main requirements:

1. Motivational potential-goals, motives and interests of the graduate.
2. Professional and qualification characteristics of a graduate.
3. Personal and intellectual characteristics of the graduate – memory, attention, perception, thinking, Will, etc.
4. Medical and biophysiological characteristics of the graduate – age, gender, character, abilities.

Based on the above dependencies, at the level of the regions, the subjects involved in the process of formation of the competitiveness of graduates of higher education institutions and their interaction can be brought into a systematized form of connection in terms of the educational services market and the labor market (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Subjects ensuring the competitiveness of graduates of higher education institutions at the level of Regions[1]

In our opinion, in the training of qualified competitive specialists in the labor market, the tasks of society and higher education require a coordinated program-targeted approach to their solution. It provides for the selection of those from many subjects of the labor market who, based on goals, tasks, competencies, ensure the formation and development of the competitiveness of graduates and contribute to the effectiveness of its implementation.

Taking into account this connection, the study examined the relationship of the state's educational, employment, job creation and non-governmental coordination systems.

The interaction of entities within the above-mentioned social partnership systematized the structure of the relations that establish and regulate the conditions, guarantees, opportunities, restrictions that effectively solve the problems of increasing the competitiveness of graduates of higher educational institutions in the labor market, determine the procedure, norms and foundations of agreed and coordinated interaction, and also the interests of the parties within the, research has been carried out on the development of socio-psychological mechanisms and tools.

Taking into account the fact that the established factor in assessing the competitiveness of graduates of higher education institutions makes it possible to realistically assess the level of competitiveness of specialists being trained in higher education institutions, an algorithm and a model has been developed and recommended for use in practice, which allows graduates with higher education to study the degree of.

The employment of graduates by higher education institutions is not carried out on an analytical basis on separate criteria and indicators due to the fact that monitoring is carried out in the process of monitoring based on the interests of the OSCE. Because the higher education institution tries to show that its graduates are fully occupied at the level possible in

the existing monitoring. In the Real case, graduates of this monitoring should be studied on the basis of criteria for employment in their specialty, non-specialty employment, free employment and competitive employment (Figure 3).

The fact that the analysis of the employment of graduates is carried out in a separate direction or specialties that are being prepared makes it possible to clearly see the state of supply and demand in the labor market in each direction or specialty, and at the same time the target aspects of employment. In other words, in graduate employment monitoring, studying the total number of graduates in a direction or specialty by separating the number of non-employed and employed graduates in the composition, the number of employed graduates in their specialty or non-specialty, the number of competitive or freely employed graduates in the amount of employed graduates in their specialty, helps to accurately assess the level of.

Figure 3. Structural model of graduates of higher education institutions by employment criterion²

The algorithm for analyzing the employment of graduates of higher education institutions, expanding the possibility of more accurately indicating the level of competitiveness of graduates, is based on an algorithm that involves sequential implementation of an assessment process consisting of four interconnected sections (goal setting, goal implementation, results analysis and management sections).

Today, the formation and improvement of the competitiveness of graduates in higher education institutions arises from strategic goals for the creation of a system for improving the competitiveness of graduates in a higher educational institution (Table 1).

Summing up the strategic goals of creating a system for improving the competitiveness of graduates of a higher educational institution, it is advisable to allocate:

- the orientation of the system to form the competitiveness of each graduate;
- the fact that the system is based on the principle of modern diagnosis of the state of competitiveness of graduates of a higher educational institution;
- the orientation of the system to increase the competitiveness of the higher education institution in the market of educational services on the basis of its prestige in the labor market.

² Developed by the author based on research.

Students admitted to the undergraduate course are advised to divide the development of competitiveness in the period up to completion of the course into 4 stages – the period for the formation of Professional Qualifications (1st year), the period for the acquisition of professional qualifications (1-3 courses), the period for the growth of professional qualifications (2-4 years) and the period for.

The priority goal of the first stage is the assimilation of the content of the orientation (specialty) by students, in achieving the goal, it is advisable to use a number of management tools, namely professional orientation of students in orientation (specialty), the organization of dating practices and career – oriented targeted seminars, stratification and professional orientation of students in talent and interest.

Table 1.

Stages of formation and improvement of competitiveness of graduates of higher educational institutions³

Strategic objectives			
Creation of a system for improving the competitiveness of graduates of a higher educational institution: - focused on the formation of the competitiveness of each graduate; - based on the principle of modern diagnosis of the state of competitiveness of graduates of a higher educational institution; - on the basis of prestige in the labor market, it is aimed at increasing the competitiveness of the higher educational institution in the market of educational services.			
Stages of improving the competitiveness of graduates of a higher educational institution			
<i>1. The period for the formation of professional qualifications in the direction (specialty) (Course 1)</i>	<i>2. Period of professional qualification in direction (specialty) (Course 1-3)</i>	<i>3. Period of growth of professional qualification in direction (specialty) (Course 2-4)</i>	<i>4. The period of achieving a highly competitive level in direction (specialization) (Course 4)</i>
Priority goals			
Appropriation of the content of orientation (specialization) by students	Assimilation of the basics of professional qualification by students	The level of professional qualification in students and the growth of research skills	The highest level of professional qualification and research skills in students
Tools for managing the competitiveness of graduates.			
Professional orientation of students in orientation (specialty). Organization of	The basis is the assimilation of professional objects. Qualification practices and organization of	Mastering of the disciplines of base and specialty (selection). Establishment of independent	The establishment of education in the master-apprentice system. To act as a specialist during the period of

³ Developed by the author.

dating practices and career-oriented targeted seminars. Stratification and professional orientation of students by talent and interest. Involvement in the research process. Assessment of the state of competitiveness.	meetings with experienced practitioners. Formation of an effective incentive system. Deepening the participation of talented students in the research process. Assessment of the state of competitiveness.	activities in qualification practice. Expansion of the effect of an effective incentive system. Transition to independent implementation of research activities. Assessment of the state of competitiveness.	qualification practice. The establishment of advisory assistance to graduates. Assessment of the state of competitiveness.
Object			
<i>Graduates of higher education institutions</i>			

The priority goal of the second stage is the assimilation of the foundations of professional qualification by students, in the achievement of which it is advisable to use the following tools:

- mastering of base professional science (modules);
- qualification practices and organization of meetings with experienced practitioners;
- formation of an effective incentive system;
- deepening the participation of talented students in the research process.

The priority goal of the third stage is to ensure the growth of the level of professional qualification and research skills in students, in which it is recommended to use the following tools:

- mastering the disciplines of base and specialty (selection);
- establishing independent activities in qualification practice;
- expand the impact of an effective incentive system;
- independent implementation of research activities.

The use of competitiveness and management models in the development of strategies to increase the competitiveness of graduates in higher education institutions, and the use of marking the employment of graduates on the basis of Real indicators, on the one hand, increases the realism of process analysis, on the other hand, ensures an increase in the effectiveness of strategic planning of graduate competitiveness for higher education institutions.

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